

The Relationship Between the Severity of Anxiety and Pregnancy Stress in Women Who Have Received the Covid-19 Vaccine During Pregnancy

Covid-19 Aşısı Yaptırmış Olan Kadınların Gebelik Dönemlerindeki Endişe Şiddeti ile Gebelik Stresi Arasındaki İlişki

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to explore the relationship between anxiety severity and pregnancy stress in women who were vaccinated for COVID-19 during the pandemic and later became pregnant, based on the hypothesis that they might perceive potential negative effects of the vaccine. This descriptive correlational study was conducted with 302 pregnant women between November 2023 and June 2024. Data were collected using a Personal Information Form, the Anxiety Severity Scale (ASS), and the Pregnancy Stress Scale (PSS). For normally distributed data, the Student's t-test was used for comparisons between two groups, while one-way ANOVA and the Bonferroni test were applied for comparisons involving three or more groups. For non-normally distributed data, the Mann-Whitney U test, Kruskal-Wallis test, and Dunn test were used, respectively. Relationships between variables were assessed using Pearson and Spearman correlation analyses. The average age of the participants was 28.56±5.02 years, and the average gestational week was 27.16±8.16, with 71.5% having received live vaccines and 28.5% having received inactivated vaccines. The average score for the ASS was 14.00±5.00 (moderate level), while the average score for the PSS was 62.30±25.61 (moderate level). A positive correlation was found among all sub-dimensions of the PSS. Significant relationships were identified between the severity of anxiety and pregnancy stress in women who were vaccinated for COVID-19 during the pandemic and later became pregnant. It was particularly noted that gestational week and income status had an impact on the sub-dimensions of pregnancy stress.

Anahtar Kelimeler:

Vaccine, COVID-19, Anxiety Severity, Pregnant, Pregnancy Stress

Öz

Bu çalışma, pandemi döneminde COVID-19 aşısı olmuş ve sonrasında gebe kalan kadınlarda, aşının olası olumsuz etkilerini algılayabilecekleri varsayımına dayanarak, endişe şiddeti ile gebelik stresi arasındaki ilişkiyi araştırmayı amaçlamaktadır. Tanımlayıcı ve ilişki arayıcı türdeki bu çalışma, Kasım 2023 ile Haziran 2024 tarihleri arasında 302 gebe kadın ile gerçekleştirilmiştir. Veriler, Kişisel Bilgi Formu, Endişe Şiddeti Ölçeği (EŞÖ) ve Gebelik Stresi Ölçeği (GSÖ) kullanılarak toplanmıştır. Normal dağılım gösteren verilerde iki grup karşılaştırmalarında Student's t-testi, üç veya daha fazla grup karşılaştırmalarında ise tek yönlü ANOVA ve Bonferroni testi kullanılmıştır. Normal dağılım göstermeyen verilerde sırasıyla Mann-Whitney U testi, Kruskal-Wallis testi ve Dunn testi uygulanmıştır. Değişkenler arasındaki ilişkiler Pearson ve Spearman korelasyon analizleri ile değerlendirilmiştir. Katılımcıların yaş ortalaması 28,56±5,02 yıl, gebelik haftası ortalaması ise 27,16±8,16 olup; %71,5'i canlı aşı, %28,5'i ise inaktif aşı yaptırmıştır. EŞÖ puan ortalaması 14,00±5,00 (orta düzeyde), GSÖ puan ortalaması ise 62,30±25,61 (orta düzeyde) bulunmuştur. GSÖ'nün tüm alt boyutları arasında pozitif bir korelasyon bulunmuştur. Pandemi döneminde COVID-19 aşısı olmuş ve sonrasında gebe kalan kadınlarda, endişe şiddeti ile gebelik stresi arasında anlamlı ilişkiler tespit edilmiştir. Özellikle gebelik haftası ve gelir durumunun gebelik stresinin alt boyutları üzerinde etkili olduğu gözlemlenmiştir.

Key Words:

Aşı, COVID-19, Endişe Şiddeti, Gebelik Stresi

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1.INTRODUCTION

The coronavirus (COVID-19) spread rapidly worldwide, leading to a pandemic and causing widespread panic (Bao et al., 2020). Studies have shown that pregnant women experienced increased levels of fear, depression, and anxiety during the COVID-19 pandemic compared to the period before the pandemic (Durmuş et al., 2022; Fan et al., 2022). Therefore, pregnant individuals have been recorded as a particularly high-risk group during this period. Although pregnancy is a natural life event, it induces physiological, psychological, and social changes, making it one of the most significant variables in a woman's life (Yanikkerem et al., 2006). During this phase, psychological, biological, and emotional changes can lead to feelings of withdrawal, anxiety, uncertainty, worry, and conflict. When these feelings are at a certain level, they can motivate individuals; however, when they exceed the average level, they can adversely affect a person's life (Şen and Şirin, 2013; Köse and Pasinlioğlu 2015). Psychological issues are defined as negative responses to stressful life conditions and are recognized as a global health concern (Khoury et al., 2023). Conditions classified as psychological issues, such as depression, stress, and anxiety, are commonly observed during prenatal and postnatal periods (Obrochta et al., 2020). It has been determined that pregnancy and childbirth increase the incidence of anxiety and mild depression, and that levels of depression and anxiety change as the gestational weeks progress (Turan ve Çetin, 2001).

Anxiety is a type of vague fear experienced without fully grasping the essence of the issue, arising from the perception of potential risky situations in the future (Taşkın, 2012; Üst ve Pasinlioğlu, 2015). The concept of stress, on the other hand, refers to a psychosocial and physiological state that causes discomfort and tension in an individual (Ünsa, 2012). Women, who are often expected to bear the burdens of both professional and family life, encounter stress more frequently. The primary reason for women facing stress is pregnancy, accounting for 53.5% of the cases (Bayık, 2006).

Pregnancy can be viewed as a developmental crisis period, which may bring joy, fulfillment, maturity, and happiness, but can also be accompanied by negative psychological emotions such as stress, anxiety, overload, and anxious anticipation (Şahin ve Kılıçarslan, 2010). In other words, it is a period of significant stress in women's lives, often associated with anxiety and depression (Sevindik, 2005). Psychological problems encountered during the prenatal period are known to contribute to obstetric complications, including intrauterine growth restriction, preterm birth, and low birth weight (Grote et al., 2010; Mélancon et al., 2020). Stress and anxiety experienced by pregnant women can negatively impact the fetus's heart rate and blood pressure, potentially resulting in preterm labor, developmental delays, low birth weight, and adverse effects on newborns (Şahin ve Kılıçarslan, 2010). Prenatal depression is a critical concern that necessitates early intervention and treatment, as it adversely affects the well-being of both the fetus and the mother, and increases the risk of postpartum depression (Ayvaz et al., 2006; Bunevicius et al., 2009). Pregnant women often experience heightened anxiety due to the intense awareness of potential dangers during labor and the postpartum period (Çetişli et al., 2016). The causes and levels of anxiety experienced during pregnancy can vary (Arfaie et al., 2017). Stress experienced during pregnancy can lead to developmental problems in children, including excessive crying, easy irritability, asocial behaviors, attention deficit hyperactivity disorder, and schizophrenia (Weinstock, 2005). Additionally, severe anxiety can contribute to preeclampsia, low-birth-weight infants, premature births, miscarriages, and developmental disorders and mental conditions in newborns (Huizink et al., 2003).

Since the COVID-19 pandemic, although vaccination efforts have continued in many countries, studies on vaccines in pregnant women have been delayed due to the uncertainty regarding potential side effects (Gurol-Urganci et al., 2021). Additionally, clinical trials have shown that immunization during pregnancy is 78-96% effective against severe complications of COVID-19 (Gurol-Urganci et al., 2021, Karasek et al., 2021). Globally, it has been observed that the COVID-19 vaccine generates a strong maternal humoral response, and no safety concerns have been noted regarding vaccinations administered during pregnancy. Research has demonstrated the effectiveness of the COVID-19 vaccine, leading to a consensus on its use during pregnancy (WHO, 2020).

Following the acceleration of the vaccine development process and the publication of Phase-3 trial results, the WHO granted emergency use authorization for six vaccines as of June 3, 2021 (WHO, 2023). Vaccines are now regarded as crucial for safeguarding the health and wellness of individuals across all age groups. The WHO states that “vaccines initiate specific biological processes that help our immune system identify and combat pathogens, such as viruses and bacteria, thereby shielding our bodies from diseases caused by these infectious agents” (WHO, 2023).

2. METHOD

2.1. Purpose of the Study

The COVID-19 pandemic underscored the critical role of vaccines and their effects, especially for pregnant women, fueling concerns about their health and the well-being of their babies. Pregnancy represents a unique phase in a woman’s life, one that requires careful decision-making to safeguard both maternal and fetal health. Maintaining good mental health during pregnancy is crucial for the overall health of both the mother and the child, as psychological issues can negatively affect the mother’s emotional state and result in poor pregnancy outcomes. This study seeks to explore the connection between anxiety levels and stress related to pregnancy, with the hypothesis that women who were vaccinated against COVID-19 during the pandemic might harbor concerns about the potential risks of the vaccine, especially if they later became pregnant.

2.2. Research Questions

1. Is there a significant relationship between the severity of anxiety and pregnancy stress in women who were vaccinated for COVID-19 during the pandemic and later became pregnant?
2. Do the type of COVID-19 vaccine (live vs. inactivated) and gestational week influence levels of anxiety and pregnancy stress?
3. How do demographic factors such as income status and gestational week affect the sub-dimensions of pregnancy stress?
4. Is there a correlation among the sub-dimensions of the Pregnancy Stress Scale in this population?

5. What is the overall level of anxiety and pregnancy stress among pregnant women who received COVID-19 vaccines prior to conception?

2.3. Study Type

This research is a descriptive correlational study.

2.4. Study Design

The study was conducted between November 2023 and June 2024 at the Family Health Center (FHC) in the city center of Karabuk, involving healthy pregnant women aged 18 and older who came for routine check-ups and consented to participate in the study.

2.5. Sample Selection

The sample size was determined using the correlation coefficient. With an assumed correlation of $r=0.30$, statistical calculations indicated that a minimum of 138 women would be required for the study, based on a 95% confidence level and a statistical power of 0.80. In the end, the study included 302 pregnant women who volunteered to take part.

2.6. Inclusion Criteria

Participants needed to be pregnant, have received the COVID-19 vaccine during the pandemic, be willing to engage in verbal communication, and provide consent to take part in the study.

2.7. Exclusion Criteria

Exclusion criteria included the presence of communication difficulties, having chronic illnesses, experiencing a high-risk pregnancy, having a psychiatric diagnosis, possessing visual or auditory impairments, and refusing to participate in the study.

2.8. Data Collection Method and Tools

Data for this research were collected through face-to-face interactions with pregnant women residing in Karabuk from November 2023 to June 2024. Participants were informed about the purpose of the study and assured that their information would be kept confidential and used solely for research. Both verbal and written consent were obtained, and following the completion of the consent form, data were gathered using a Personal Information Form, the Anxiety Severity Scale (ASS), and the Pregnancy Stress Scale (PSS). The scales have been used after obtaining the necessary permissions.

2.8.1. Personal Information Form

This form includes 12 questions addressing various variables such as age, education level, employment status, family structure, income, gestational age, and the type of vaccine received.

2.8.2. Anxiety Severity Scale (ASS)

The Anxiety Severity Scale is a self-report scale developed to evaluate dysfunctional anxiety associated with psychopathologies and emotional distress. It comprises eight items assessed using a 4-point Likert scale, where participants rate the items based on how applicable they are to their general state, ranging from 0 (definitely not true) to 3 (absolutely true). Higher scores on the scale indicate a greater severity of anxiety. The Turkish adaptation, validity, and reliability studies were conducted by Tunay and Soygüt (2009), with a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.88 established for the scale. In this study, the Cronbach's alpha was found to be 0.875.

2.8.3. Pregnancy Stress Scale (PSS)

The Pregnancy Stress Scale developed by Chen (2015) consists of 36 items across 5 subdimensions and is used to identify stress factors related to pregnancy [30]. The subdimensions (SD) are as follows:

SD-1: Stress arising from the search for a safe process during pregnancy, labor, and delivery for both mother and baby (Items 1-9).

SD-2: Stress related to infant care and changing family dynamics (Items 10-18).

SD-3: Stress arising from the definition of the motherhood role (Items 19-26).

SD-4: Stress resulting from the search for social support (Items 27-30).

SD-5: Stress due to changes in physical appearance and functioning (Items 31-36).

Items on the scale are answered on a 5-point Likert scale. The degree of anxiety, distress, and worry experienced by pregnant women is rated from "definitely no" to "very severe," with scores ranging from 0 to 4. The perceived stress levels during pregnancy can vary from a minimum of 0 to a maximum of 144. The scale is used to identify pregnancy-related stress factors; higher scores indicate increased stress. In this study, the Cronbach's alpha was found to be 0.890.

2.9. Data Analysis

Statistical analyses were conducted utilizing the SPSS 27.0 software package. Continuous data from the study were summarized with means and standard deviations, while categorical data were represented as percentage distributions. To check for normality, histograms were created, and the values of Skewness and Kurtosis were analyzed. Values of Skewness and Kurtosis within the range of +1.0 to -1.0 were deemed normal (George ve Mallery, 2019). For data with a normal distribution, the Student's t-test was used to compare two categorical variables, while one-way ANOVA was used for comparisons across three or more categories. The Bonferroni test was conducted to determine which specific group accounted for any observed differences. For data that did not follow a normal distribution, the Mann-Whitney U test was used to compare two categories, while the Kruskal-Wallis test was employed for comparisons involving three or more categories, followed by the Dunn test to identify

the group contributing to the differences. Pearson and Spearman correlation analyses were used to evaluate relationships between variables. A statistical significance level of $p < 0.05$ was established.

3. RESULTS

Table 1 displays the descriptive characteristics of women who were vaccinated against COVID-19 during the pandemic and later became pregnant.

When examining the descriptive characteristics of the pregnant women, the average age was found to be 28.56 ± 5.02 years (18-43), and the average gestational week was 27.16 ± 8.16 weeks (10-40). It was determined that 35.8% had a university education or higher, 65.9% were homemakers, 12.3% belonged to an extended family type, 10.3% had an income less than their expenses, 22.5% had experienced at least one miscarriage during their lifetime, and 71.5% had received a live vaccine (Table 1).

Table 1. Descriptive characteristics of pregnant women

Variables	Mean±SS	Min-Max
Age	28.56±5.02	18-43
Gestational week	27.16±8.16	10-40
Number of pregnancies	2.03±1.20	1-9
Number of living children	0.86±0.94	0-5
	N	%
Education Level		
Primary School	18	6.0
Secondary School	72	23.8
High School	104	34.4
University and above	108	35.8
Employment Status		
Public Sector	42	13.9
Private Sector	49	16.2
Self-employed	12	4.0
Homeworker	199	65.9
Family Type		
Nuclear	265	87.7
Extended	37	12.3
Income Level		
Income less than expenses	31	10.3
Income equal to expenses	222	73.5
Income greater than expenses	49	16.2
Vaccine Type		
Live vaccine	216	71.5
Inactivated vaccine	86	28.5
History of Miscarriage		
Yes	68	22.5
No	234	77.5

SS: Standard deviation, Min: Minimum, Max: Maximum

The mean ASS score of the pregnant women was found to be 14.00±5.00, while the mean PSS score was 62.30±25.61. The mean scores of the PSS subdimensions were as follows: 20.28±9.12, 14.46±8.29, 12.63±6.65, 4.89±4.67, and 10.88±5.84, respectively (Table 2).

Table 2. Average scores of women on the ASS and PSS subdimensions

Scales	The minimum and maximum scores obtained from the scale	Mean±SS
ASS	0-24	14.02±5.04
PSS	0-149	62.30±25.61
Subdimension-1	0-79	20.28±9.12
Subdimension-2	0-48	14.46±8.29
Subdimension-3	0-56	12.63±6.65
Subdimension-4	0-35	4.89±4.67
Subdimension-5	0-24	10.88±5.84

SS: Standard deviation; ASS: Anxiety Severity Scale; PSS: Pregnancy Stress Scale

When examining the mean ASS scores in relation to the descriptive characteristics of the pregnant women, no statistically significant associations were found. A comparison of the mean scores for subdimension-1 of the PSS with gestational week indicated a statistically significant low-level negative correlation ($P=0.001$). A statistically significant difference ($P=0.009$) was also identified in the mean scores of PSS subdimension-1 when comparing participants based on employment status. A post-hoc analysis (Benferroni) conducted to identify the source of this difference revealed that it existed between housewives and private sector employees (Table 3).

A statistically significant difference ($P=0.014$) was found when analyzing the mean scores of the 5th sub-dimension of the PSS in relation to income status. The post-hoc analysis revealed that this difference existed between individuals whose income matched their expenses and those whose income was greater than their expenses (Table 3).

Table 3. Comparison of the descriptive characteristics of pregnant women with the mean scores of ASS and PSS subdimensions

Variables	ASS	PSS SD-1	PSS SD-2	PSS SD-3	PSS SD-4	PSS SD-5
Age	$r_p=0.031$ $P=0.586$	$r_{ps}=-0.073$ $P=0.203$	$r_p=-0.038$ $P=0.512$	$r_{ps}=0.006$ $P=0.921$	$r_{ps}=0.018$ $P=0.759$	$r_p=-0.063$ $P=0.276$
Gestational week	$r_p=-0.051$ $P=0.378$	$r_{ps}=-0.184$ $P=0.001$	$r_p=0.014$ $P=0.802$	$r_{ps}=0.102$ $P=0.077$	$r_{ps}=0.016$ $P=0.779$	$r_p=0.107$ $P=0.064$
Education Level	14.66±1.17	18.11±2.33	15.11±2.18	12.33±1.83	4.77±1.15	9.50±1.39
Primary School ¹	12.94±0.51	19.77±1.10	14.54±0.99	12.76±0.83	4.66±0.54	10.36±0.72
Secondary School ²	13.71±0.55	20.81±0.92	14.59±0.80	12.52±0.64	4.88±0.49	11.82±0.58
High School ³	14.89±0.44	20.48±0.82	14.17±0.79	12.70±0.66	4.99±0.41	11.23±0.55
University and above ⁴	$F=2.480$ $P=0.061$	$X^2=2.252$ $P=0.522$	$F=0.90$ $P=0.966$	$X^2=0.050$ $P=0.997$	$X^2=0.754$ $P=0.860$	$F=1.333$ $P=0.264$
Employment Status	14.66±0.77	21.35±1.11	13.16±1.22	12.57±0.74	5.47±0.66	10.26±0.88
Public Sector ¹	13.53±0.75	23.20±1.15	14.87±0.90	12.44±0.52	4.42±0.54	11.26±0.85
Private Sector ²	15.08±1.29	22.41±2.65	16.00±2.09	12.75±1.53	6.33±1.20	13.66±1.39
Self-employed ³	13.92±0.35	19.21±0.67	14.54±0.62	12.68±0.53	4.80±0.35	11.12±0.43
Housewife ⁴	$F=0.591$ $P=0.622$	$X^2=11.609$ $P=0.009$ $4>2$	$F=0.523$ $P=667$	$X^2=0.008$ $P=1.000$	$X^2=4.225$ $P=0.238$	$F=1.027$ $P=0.381$

Family Type	13.84±0.31	20.46±0.56	14.55±0.51	12.56±0.41	4.94±0.28	
Nuclear	15.18±0.73	19.05±1.36	13.83±1.29	13.10±0.93	4.54±0.71	11.32±0.37
Extended	T=-1.532 P=0.127	Z=-1.094 P=0.274	T=0.489 P=0.625	Z=-0.946 P=0.344	Z=-0.442 P=0.659	9.72±0.88
Income Level	13.67±0.87	21.03±2.58	16.19±1.26	13.61±0.97	5.58±0.85	12.80±1.27
Income less than expenses ¹	14.20±0.33	20.25±0.57	14.16±0.56	12.15±0.42	4.70±0.31	10.52±0.38
Income equal to expenses ²	13.32±0.69	19.97±1.09	14.73±1.24	14.18±1.19	5.34±0.66	12.77±0.79
Income greater than expenses ³	F=.695 P=0.500	X ² =1.300 P=0.522	F=0.845 P=0.430	X ² =2.574 P=0.276	X ² =2.054 P=0.358	F=4.310 P=0.014 2>3
Vaccine Type	14.37±0.33	20.12±0.64	14.61±0.57	12.40±0.42	5.12±0.32	
Live vaccine	13.83±0.57	20.69±0.88	14.09±0.86	13.20±0.81	4.31±0.44	11.29±0.40
Inactivated vaccine	T=0.378 P=0.736	Z=-0.615 P=0.538	T=0.489 P=0.625	Z=-0.731 P=0.465	Z=-1.397 P=0.162	10.69±0.64 T=0.786 P=0.432
History of Miscarriage	14.00±0.55	18.58±1.01	15.13±1.08	13.04±0.77	4.95±0.59	11.40±0.77
Yes	14.02±0.33	20.79±0.60	14.20±0.52	12.47±0.43	4.84±0.30	11.00±0.38
No	T=-0.031 P=0.936	Z=-1.634 P=0.102	T=0.811 P=0.418	Z=-0.400 P=0.689	Z=-0.120 P=0.904	T=0.483 P=0.630

ASS:Anxiety Severity Scale; PSS:Pregnancy Stress Scale; SD:Subdimensions; F=One-Way ANOVA Test; T=Independent Samples Test; Z=Mann-Whitney U Test, X²=Kruskal-Wallis Test; rp:Pearson Correlation; rs:Spearman's Correlation; ASS: Anxiety Severity Scale; PSS: Pregnancy Stress Scale

A low-level positive correlation was identified between the ASS scores of pregnant women and subdimension-1 of the PSS. Additionally, moderate positive correlations were found between subdimensions-1 and 2 of the PSS, as well as between subdimension-3 and the first two subdimensions. Subdimension-4 showed a low-level positive correlation with subdimension-1 and a moderate positive correlation with subdimension-3, while also exhibiting a high-level positive correlation with subdimensions-2 and 5. A high-level positive correlation was observed between subdimensions-3 and 4, along with a moderate correlation with subdimension-5. Lastly, a strong positive correlation was noted between subdimensions-4 and 5 of the PSS (Table 4).

Table 4. Relationship between mean scores of ASS and PSS subdimensions

Scales	1	2	3	4	5	6
Anxiety Severity Scale						1
PSS Subdimension-1 (Stress from safe process)	0.148*	1				
PSS Subdimension-2 (Stress from baby care and safe family relationships)	0.110	0.428**	1			
PSS Subdimension-3 (Stress from the motherhood role)	0.053	0.439**	0.616**	1		
PSS Subdimension-4 (Stress from seeking social support)	0.063	0.207**	0.626**	0.618**	1	
PSS Subdimension-5 (Stress from physical appearance/function changes)	0.109	0.255**	0.622**	0.474**	0.568**	1

*, significant at the 0.005 level; **, significant at the 0.001 level, Spearman's correlation analysis was used; ASS: Anxiety Severity Scale; PSS: Pregnancy Stress Scale

4. DISCUSSION

Stress during pregnancy can harm the health of the mother, the unborn child, and the newborn. Research suggests that prenatal stress is linked to adverse outcomes such as miscarriage, antenatal

bleeding, increased resistance in uterine arteries, hypertensive conditions during pregnancy, placental issues, preterm labor, challenging deliveries, surgical births, restricted fetal growth, low APGAR scores, low birth weight, fetal loss, and postpartum depression (Ortaarık, 2012; Yali & Lobel, 2002). Moreover, a stressful pregnancy can result in long-term health issues that may manifest during childhood, adolescence, and adulthood. Early identification of women at risk allows for preventive interventions and early action. This, in turn, can help prevent or mitigate the adverse outcomes of stress on labor and the postpartum period (Atasever ve Sis, 2018; Woods, 2010).

This study explored the connection between anxiety severity and pregnancy stress among women who received the COVID-19 vaccine and later became pregnant during the pandemic. The results offered valuable insights by analyzing how the descriptive characteristics of pregnant women relate to their levels of stress.

In this study, the average ASS score of the pregnant participants was 14.00 ± 5.00 , suggesting that they generally had moderate levels of anxiety. The absence of a statistically significant association between the descriptive characteristics and ASS scores indicates that more complex factors may be involved. This result suggests that anxiety levels among pregnant women were fairly consistent, irrespective of their demographic characteristics. Similarly, Demirel et al. (2022) observed that pregnant women experienced moderate levels of anxiety during the COVID-19 pandemic.

The study found no significant correlation between the age of pregnant women and their average scores on the ASS and PSS subscales. Likewise, no meaningful correlation was identified between the educational level of pregnant women and their mean scores on these subscales. The literature reflects similar results, showing no significant differences between education level and stress (Çapık, 2013; Shishehgar, 2014; Ahmed, 2017; Bakır, 2021). However, some studies have pointed to different results, suggesting that educational level can influence stress levels (Pais, 2014; Bodaghi, 2017; Sis & Atasever, 2020). These observations imply that the link between educational level and perceived stress in pregnant women might be related to enhanced self-control and higher self-esteem as educational attainment increases.

In this study, it was found that as the weeks of pregnancy increased, stress related to pregnancy, the labor process, and the search for a safe experience for both mother and baby (mean score of PSS SD-1) decreased. Some studies have reported that pregnant women with gestational weeks less than 12 have higher stress levels (Engidaw ve Mekonnen, 2019). Atasever and Sis (2018) also noted a significant difference between gestational weeks and pregnancy-related stress. This finding suggests that with the progression of pregnancy, especially the stress related to pregnancy and childbirth decreases, indicating that stress levels may decrease with increasing adaptation and experience during the pregnancy process. Conversely, Bakır et al. (2021) found no significant difference between the month of pregnancy and the stress observed during pregnancy. In a similar vein, Ahmed et al. (2017) found no association between the trimester of pregnancy and perceived stress levels. However, these studies did not explore the impact of receiving the COVID-19 vaccine, highlighting a distinctive aspect of our research compared to others.

When comparing the employment status with the average scores of PSS SD-1, it was observed that housewives had higher average scores than women working in the private sector. The higher stress

in housewives arising from pregnancy, labor process, and the search for a safe process for both mother and baby may be due to these women spending more time at home and being unable to share their concerns with anyone due to a lack of socialization. It can be considered that housewives' lack of access to current job and social support systems may affect their stress levels. Additionally, in the study by Sis and Atasever (2020), it was found that being employed in a income-generating job did not affect the perceived stress levels before childbirth. Elkin (2015) indicated that the employment status of pregnant women affects their ability to cope with stress and that education provided by the healthcare team can facilitate the reduction of anxiety and make it easier for pregnant women to cope with stress.

It has been determined that those whose income exceeds their expenses have lower stress levels (average score of PSS SD-5) related to changes in physical appearance and function than those whose income equals their expenses. This finding suggests that financial stability is essential for the psychological well-being of pregnant women. The observed difference between those whose income equals their expenses and those whose income exceeds their expenses indicates that economic resources play a critical role in stress management during pregnancy. This suggests that financial security may influence stress arising from physical changes related to pregnancy. In the study by Sis and Atasever (2020), it was observed that pregnant women with poor economic conditions had higher perceived stress levels before childbirth.

The study showed no significant differences among pregnant women based on the type of COVID-19 vaccine they received. Overall, it found that whether the vaccine was live or inactivated had no impact on anxiety and stress levels during pregnancy. Additionally, there were no notable differences when comparing the effects of live versus inactivated vaccines.

Regarding miscarriage, it was determined that having experienced a miscarriage in a previous pregnancy had no effect on the levels of anxiety and stress in the current pregnancy. No studies related to this situation were found in the literature.

The average PSS score for pregnant women was determined to be at a moderate level (62.30 ± 25.61), and a positive correlation was observed among all subdimensions of the PSS. Furthermore, it was noted that as the anxiety levels of pregnant women rose, the mean scores of all PSS subdimensions also increased. Uncertainty is a condition that increases stress levels. In women, this uncertainty is known as the pregnancy period, and it can be thought that this uncertainty increases stress in women. These findings indicate that pregnancy stress is a complex and multifaceted phenomenon, and various stress factors may interact with each other. Although the COVID-19 vaccination status was not investigated, a study by Bakir et al. (2021) reported that the overall average PSS score for pregnant women was 94.96 ± 7.22 (45%). In the research conducted by Tartici and Beydag (2020) during the COVID-19 period, the Perceived Stress Scale score was reported as 32.53 ± 4.7 (with a maximum score of 56), suggesting that perceived stress levels among pregnant women were notably high. In contrast, Baran et al. (2020) found the Perceived Stress Scale score of pregnant women to be 21.0.

In conclusion, this study did not yield significant results regarding the ASS and PSS of pregnant women who received the COVID-19 vaccine before pregnancy; however, many factors affecting the stress levels of pregnant women have been identified, which are believed to illuminate future research. Additionally, the integration of various social, economic, and psychological support systems during pregnancy can be considered an important strategy for improving maternal health.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This research explored the connection between the severity of anxiety and stress related to pregnancy in women who received the COVID-19 vaccine during the pandemic and later became pregnant. It also evaluated how different demographic factors influenced pregnancy stress. The results indicate significant relationships between women's anxiety levels and particular subdimensions of pregnancy stress. No significant differences were identified among pregnant women regarding the type of vaccine administered during the COVID-19 period. This situation suggests that anxiety levels are similar regardless of demographic factors. In the relationship between gestational age and pregnancy stress, it was observed that stress related to pregnancy and the labor process decreased as gestational age progressed. This indicates that increasing adaptation and experience during the pregnancy process may reduce stress levels. A significant difference was found between employment status and pregnancy stress. Different stress levels were observed between housewives and women working in the private sector. It can be inferred that the higher stress levels in housewives may stem from a lack of job and social support systems. A notable difference was found between income level and stress related to physical changes. The difference between those whose income equals their expenses and those whose income exceeds their expenses suggests that financial security may influence stress related to physical changes during pregnancy. High levels of positive relationships were found among the subdimensions of pregnancy stress. This finding demonstrates that different dimensions of pregnancy stress interact strongly with each other and that stress factors are interconnected.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

Psychological support and stress management programs should be developed for housewives and women in low-income groups. These programs should aim to strengthen social support networks and reduce the stress factors during the pregnancy process. Regardless of income status, financial support and counseling services should be offered to women who struggle to adapt to physical changes during pregnancy. Such support may help alleviate stress caused by physical changes. Education and informational programs regarding the pregnancy process should be organized for both working women and housewives. These programs should be designed to provide information about stress factors related to pregnancy and to teach management strategies. Stress management interventions targeting the various subdimensions of pregnancy stress should be prioritized. Specifically, further research is needed to examine how changes occurring as gestational age advances impact stress levels.

These recommendations present actionable strategies aimed at reducing stress and anxiety levels experienced by women during pregnancy and improving their overall well-being.

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